

There is Always a prime between n^2 and $(n+1)^2$

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ABSTRACT

I give an answer in the affirmative to the following unanswered question:

Is there always a prime between n^2 and $(n+1)^2$ Where n is natural number?

The question represents a famous unsolved problem in Mathematics.

I employ some familiar ideas in Number Theory.

Mathematics Subject Classification: Number Theory, General Mathematics.

PROOF

Seeking for a contradiction, I assume that there exists a natural number n , such that there exist no prime numbers between n^2 and $(n+1)^2$

I apply the well-known theorem:

There is a constant A such that:

$$(1) \quad \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p} = \log \log x + A + O\left(\frac{1}{\log x}\right) \text{ for all } x \geq 2$$

O is the big oh notation, The summation is taken over all primes

P less than or equal to x . The "log" is the natural logarithm.

According to formula (1)

$$(2) \quad \sum_{p \leq n^2} \frac{1}{p} = \log \log n^2 + A + O\left(\frac{1}{\log n^2}\right)$$

$$(3) \quad \sum_{p \leq (n+1)^2} \frac{1}{p} = \log \log ((n+1)^2) + A + O\left(\frac{1}{\log (n+1)^2}\right)$$

Since I have assumed that there exist no prime numbers between

n^2 and $(n+1)^2$, we deduce that the left – hand sides of (2) and (3) are equal, hence.

$$(4) \quad \log \log n^2 + A + O\left(\frac{1}{\log n^2}\right) = \log \log ((n+1)^2) + A + O\left(\frac{1}{\log(n+1)^2}\right)$$

Hence we get

$$(5) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = O\left(\frac{1}{\log n^2}\right) - O\left(\frac{1}{\log(n+1)^2}\right)$$

We know that

$$(6) \quad \frac{\pi(x)}{x} = O\left(\frac{1}{\log x}\right) \text{ for all } x \geq 2$$

$\pi(x)$ is the number of primes less than or equal to x

Now I assume that $(n+1)$ is prime.

Thus

$$(7) \quad \pi(n+1) = \pi(n) + 1$$

We have that

$$(8) \quad \frac{\pi(n^2)}{n^2} = O\left(\frac{1}{\log n^2}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{2 \log n}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{\log n}\right)$$

$$(9) \quad \frac{\pi((n+1)^2)}{(n+1)^2} = O\left(\frac{1}{\log(n+1)^2}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{2 \log(n+1)}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{\log(n+1)}\right)$$

Hence equation (5) becomes

$$(10) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = O\left(\frac{1}{\log n}\right) - O\left(\frac{1}{\log(n+1)}\right)$$

We know that, since $\log$ is the natural logarithm, and since the function

$\left(\frac{1}{\log n} - \frac{1}{\log(n+1)}\right)$ is a decreasing function,

$$(11) \quad \left(\frac{1}{\log n} - \frac{1}{\log(n+1)}\right) < \frac{1}{2(n+1)} \text{ for all } n > 10$$

we know also that

$$(12) \quad O\left(\frac{1}{\log n}\right) = \frac{\pi(n)}{n}$$

$$(13) \quad O\left(\frac{1}{\log(n+1)}\right) = \frac{\pi(n+1)}{(n+1)}$$

Now using (11), (12), and (13), we can rewrite equation (10) in the form:

$$(14) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = \frac{\pi(n)}{(n)} - \frac{\pi(n+1)}{(n+1)} + t \text{ (for } n > 10)$$

where t is small number ($t < \frac{1}{2(n+1)}$)

if we substitute from equation (7) we get:

$$(15) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = \frac{\pi(n)}{(n)} - \frac{\pi(n)+1}{(n+1)} + t = \frac{\pi(n)}{n(n+1)} - \frac{1}{(n+1)} + t$$

that is

$$(16) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = \frac{1}{(n+1)} \left(\frac{\pi(n)}{(n)} - 1 + t(n+1) \right)$$

since

$$(17) \quad \frac{\pi(n)}{(n)} < 0.5 \text{ for } n > 10$$

and

$$(18) \quad t(n+1) < \frac{1}{2(n+1)} \times (n+1) = 0.5$$

We conclude that the right – hand side of equation (16) is negative, and its left – hand side is positive. Hence we arrive at a contradiction.

Now I assume that (n+1) is a composite number. Let r be the greatest prime less than or equal to n.

According to a theorem in Number Theory, if k is a natural number, then there is a prime between k and 2k.

Hence if n is even we have:

$$(19) \quad \frac{n}{2} \leq r < n$$

and if n is odd

$$(20) \quad \frac{n-1}{2} \leq r \leq n$$

In both cases we have

$$(21) \quad O\left(\frac{1}{\log r}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{\log(n+1)}\right)$$

$$(22) \quad O\left(\frac{1}{\log(r-1)}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{\log n}\right)$$

substituting in equation (10) we get

$$(23) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = O\left(\frac{1}{\log(r-1)}\right) - O\left(\frac{1}{\log r}\right)$$

we know that:

$$(24) \quad \frac{\pi(r)}{r} = O\left(\frac{1}{\log r}\right)$$

$$(25) \quad \frac{\pi(r-1)}{(r-1)} = O\left(\frac{1}{\log(r-1)}\right)$$

we know that, since log is the natural logarithm, and since the function:

$\left(\frac{1}{\log(r-1)}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{\log r}\right)$ is a decreasing function,

$$(26) \quad \left(\frac{1}{\log(r-1)}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{\log r}\right) < \frac{1}{2r} \text{ for all } r > 10$$

Now using (24), (25), and (26), we can rewrite equation (23) in the form:

$$(27) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = \frac{\pi(r-1)}{(r-1)} - \frac{\pi(r)}{r} + t \text{ (for } r > 10)$$

where t is small number ($t < \frac{1}{2r}$)

But we know that

$$(28) \quad \pi(r) = \pi(r-1) + 1$$

hence equation (27) takes the form:

$$(29) \quad \begin{aligned} \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 &= \frac{\pi(r-1)}{(r-1)} - \frac{\pi(r-1)+1}{r} + t \\ &= \frac{\pi(r-1)}{r(r-1)} - \frac{1}{r} + t \\ &= \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\pi(r-1)}{(r-1)} - 1 + tr \right) \end{aligned}$$

that is

$$(30) \quad \log \log ((n+1)^2) - \log \log n^2 = \frac{1}{r} + \left(\frac{\pi(r-1)}{(r-1)} - 1 + tr\right)$$

we know that

$$(31) \quad \left(\frac{\pi(r-1)}{(r-1)} \right) - < 0.5 \text{ for } r > 11$$

and

$$(32) \quad t < \frac{1}{2r}$$

that is

$$(33) \quad tr < 0.5$$

hence we conclude that the right – hand side of equation (30) is negative, and its left – hand side is positive. This is a contradiction.

This ends my proof.

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